

EMPLOYEES' EMPLOYMENT REASONS FOR STAYING AND LEAVING THE COMPANIES: A DESCRIPTIVE-CORRELATIONAL STUDY

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Employees' Employment Reasons for Staying and Leaving the Companies: A Descriptive-Correlational Study

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Abstract

The aim of this study was to see if there was a correlation between the demographic profiles and employment reasons for staying and leaving the companies and the difference between employees' employment reasons for staying and leaving in the companies. This study employed a correlational approach to analyze the answers of 44 employed or with prior work, 20 years old and above, working or having worked in any of the following settings: a school, an office/corporate, a clinic, or a guidance setting. According to this study's findings, only had a weak significant relationship of salary range among the variables are growth and development with the Pearson r of (ROS=0.33) with a p -value of 0.030 and (ROL=0.34) with a p -value of 0.026. The computed values are found to be a significant, the null hypothesis is rejected by the study's researchers. Therefore, we can infer that salary range has a significant relationship with growth and development both for Reason for staying and leaving. Furthermore, growth and development with a p -value of 0.045, work life balance with a p -value of 0.008, and boss/superior reasons for staying and leaving with a p -value of 0.000 has a significant difference, the researchers reject the null hypothesis as well. Therefore, we can infer that the employees' reason for staying and leaving the company are both or either the following: growth and development, work life balance and boss/superior. As one of the recommendations, the researcher suggests posting flyers, hosting meetings with various staff groups to discuss the retention strategy and posting the policy on the business website. The task of putting the plan into action can fall under the purview of a department or committee. It is crucial to make sure that those in charge of the implementation process have received the necessary training to comprehend the problems that arise in the workplace.

Keywords: *growth and development, compensation and benefits, work life balance, boss/superior, co-workers*

Introduction

Many companies devote a lot of effort and resources to determining the reasons behind employee attrition, such as through exit interviewing programs. The goal of this research is often to determine why individuals depart. Employees frequently stay with a firm until some external factor compels them. This idea is quite like the concept of inertia in the physical sciences: a body will remain in its current state until it is affected by force. First, there is the matter of employment satisfaction inside the organization. The second factor is the workplace atmosphere and how comfortable each employee is there (Hughes, 2021). However, this research is also looking for other factors that is indicated in the research questions of this study. Knowing the reasons behind employee departures is crucial since a high turnover rate might indicate that workers are not happy with their jobs. Employers would benefit from finding strategies to retain their present staff on board because it takes time and effort to locate new personnel to fill these positions. Employers may immediately address a recurrent problem and create a more enjoyable work environment by being aware of why people depart.

In addition, employee retention has emerged as a critical problem in today's business environment of intense competition. Any company that wants to control staff turnover successfully and efficiently must develop employee retention measures. In the current environment, corporates are very concerned about employee retention. Because staff retention policies have a direct impact on an employer's financial line, a firm may gain significantly from them. A high turnover rate can be quite costly. However, it's also crucial to understand why employees quit their employers since doing so may assist those businesses in better understanding the requirements of their staff.

To survive and even grow in the wake of the COVID-19 pandemic, companies have had to become creative. Many workers have changed their minds about the ideal workplace in terms of location and style. This information is based on the most recent data from Job street's Decoding Global Talent report. For instance, in April 2021, a staggering 4 million individuals in the United States left their employment in a phenomenon dubbed "The Great Resignation." A lot of workers have been thinking about how they may improve their work-life balance and whether they can work remotely. So, there is the difficulty of changing apathy into commitment. The percentage of Filipino workers who preferred to work on-site before the pandemic was 58%. Nevertheless, a greater number of people now choose working remotely (49% as of 2018). Even more so, a sizeable minority would rather have a hybrid arrangement, combining remote and on-site employment (48%). The second half of the study "Decoding Global Talent" provides the basis for this. Workers now think about this when they reflect on their current position. They would like an operational system that accommodates their preferred workplace. Consequently, if forced to labor on-site, a remote worker may decide to quit. Even in the Philippines, 29% of workers are on the hunt for new employment, showing signs of discontent and seeking greater wages to keep up with the rising cost of living. This means that the "Great Resignation" is far from done (Crismundo, 2023).

The researchers want to achieve the following objectives of this study; (1) To determine the employees' employment reasons for Staying in the companies, (2) To determine the employees' employment reasons for Leaving in the companies, (3) To make potential suggestions on how the company or organization might lower the rate of employee resignations. Companies may use this research to

their advantage in two ways: first, to keep their current personnel and second, to improve their training and programs in response to employee and industry demands.

Research Questions

In this study, using the descriptive-correlational study, the researchers sought to answer the following research questions:

1. What are the demographic profiles of respondents in terms of:
 - 1.1. age;
 - 1.2. sex;
 - 1.3. field (school/industry/clinical/guidance);
 - 1.4. tenure; and
 - 1.5. salary range?
2. How do the respondents rate their Employment Reasons for staying and leaving in the following terms:
 - 2.1. growth and development;
 - 2.2. compensation and benefits;
 - 2.3. work life balance;
 - 2.4. boss/superior; and
 - 2.5. good relationship with the co-workers?
3. Is there a significant relationship between the demographic profiles and employment reasons for staying and leaving the companies?
4. Is there a significant difference between employees' employment reasons for staying and leaving in the companies?

Literature Review

To gain insight into how to approach this study and find practical solutions to the issue at hand, this review of related literature and studies incorporates general discussions about the pertinent studies made in the past about Employees' Employment Reasons for Staying and Leaving in the Companies.

Growth and Development

Employee development refers to the process wherein staff members, with the help of their company, participate in formal training programs or explore learning opportunities to advance their knowledge, skills, and careers. According to Heinz (2021), professional development encompasses more than just tailoring a person's skill set to a certain job. Instead, it refers to ongoing education that develops individuals and aids in their advancement along unique career routes. Although the ultimate duty for professional development rests with the person, it is advantageous for the employer to support ongoing education by offering or supporting both internal and external learning opportunities. Making staff development a top priority guarantees that team members' abilities keep developing in line with business trends and best practices. Consider the fact that every few years, medical practitioners must repeat board certification examinations to ensure their knowledge remains current.

It is supported by Goldberg, 2021 stated by nobody wants a job that leads nowhere at a business that doesn't appreciate its employees. The Great Resignation has been dubbed as a record-breaking number of workers are presently quitting their employment in pursuit of better work-life balance, income, and perks. Lack of opportunity for professional growth is another reason why workers are leaving their employment. 45 percent of respondents to a fall 2021 poll by Monster said they would be more inclined to stay at their present work if they were given extra training. By advancing their careers, your workers will give you better work and increased retention.

According to Clear Company, 74% of workers believe that their ability to grow professionally keeps them from realizing their full potential. Few employees will feel valued and undeveloped since only 29% of firms have defined learning and development goals, which will undoubtedly lead to a disengaged workforce and high turnover rates. Making an investment in employee development not only makes your top personnel feel good about developing their abilities, but it may also lead to important promotions that help you keep hold of your best employees. According to Clear Company, 94% of employees would remain longer at organizations that engaged in staff development. A desirable employee perk is staff development. They will find someone who will if you don't start growing your staff and your team.

Compensation and Benefits

Most businesses' pay models consist of more than just salaries. Kudos (2019) stated that one cannot disregard commissions, bonuses, or allowances. This implies that a person's wage for many jobs isn't only their annual take-home pay. A terrific benefits package, quarterly or annual bonuses, monthly wellness allowances, and other items can also be included.

Leonard (2019) also supported the study, according to him, employers who are savvy understand that attracting and retaining outstanding workers entails offering a competitive salary and benefits package. Wages, salaries, bonuses, and commission plans all fall under the category of compensation. Employers shouldn't overlook the benefits component of employee compensation and benefits since these add value to employment contracts by addressing the needs of most workers.

Money supports people's personal lives and influences many of their decisions made outside of the workplace. It is also a crucial factor that individuals consider while deciding where to work. In addition, people are always trying to position themselves financially in the best possible way. People that are worth a certain income will frequently look for jobs that pay what they are worth. Properly compensating employees shows you value them as workers and as human beings. When people feel valued, they feel better about coming in to work. Overall company morale increases and people are motivated to come to work and do a good job. Additionally, when employees know there are bonuses or commissions, they are increasingly motivated to deliver grander results. Bonus and commission compensation plans become a focal point for success. When workers are paid well and are content, they are more likely to stick with the business. One reason why worker stick with companies is fair remuneration (Boitnott, 2019).

Aside from courteous treatment, in determining work satisfaction, according to 63 percent of U.S. employees, is income and benefits, according to the Society for Human Resource Management. Since they have a direct bearing on an employee's performance and motivation at work, compensation and benefits are significant factors in determining how satisfied an employee is with their employment. Therefore, it is crucial that an HR department make sure the pay and perks provided to its employees are desirable enough to maintain a good level of morale. Employees will be assured that the firm values them and appreciates the job they perform if this is done. After all, a company's most asset is its people (Wooll, 2022).

Chamberlain (2017) refuted previous studies on benefits and compensation, the culture and values of the firm, closely followed by the caliber of senior leadership and the career chances at the company, are the top predictors of workplace happiness across all income levels, which is one of their research's most startling findings. Compensation and benefits were consistently evaluated as being among the least essential workplace. The revelation that compensation is not the primary factor influencing employee happiness will not shock economists. In the Theory of Moral Sentiments, which he wrote more than 250 years ago, Adam Smith famously cautioned that monetary success frequently makes people unhappy rather than happier. A 2010 study by Princeton University researchers found that, up to a yearly income of around \$75,000, having a greater income enhances happiness. Beyond that, increased income has less of an impact on happiness as other factors take over.

Work Life Balance

Employees who have a good work-life balance are more likely to feel content when they report to work. Consequently, stress levels and the likelihood of burnout are decreased. As stated by Sanfilippo (2022), balancing your professional and personal life can be challenging, but it's essential. However, striking a healthy balance between work and life—also known as work-life integration—is essential if we are to enhance not just our physical, emotional, and mental health, but also our career. In addition, in accordance with Hill (2019), companies should make an effort to improve working environments because employees spend so much time there each week.

Many executives believe it is time to reinvent what work-life balance looks like as the millennial generation is expected to make up 75% of the workforce by 2025. A healthy work environment includes a good work-life balance. Keeping a healthy work-life balance lowers stress and prevents burnout at work. Burnout at work results from prolonged periods of high stress. Burnout is a major concern for workers who put in a lot of overtime. Fatigue, erratic moods, anger, and a decline in job performance are all signs of burnout. This is terrible news for businesses since, according to Harvard Business Review, the cost of healthcare in the United States for psychological and physical issues caused by burned-out workers ranges from \$125 billion to \$190 billion annually.

The company can boost employee engagement by assisting staffs in finding the ideal work-life balance. Companies with highly engaged employees had a near 52 percent gap in performance improvement in operating income, according to Tower Perrin's 2006 global survey. Additionally, "Companies with high levels of employee engagement improved 19.2 percent in operating income while companies with low levels of employee engagement declined 32.7 percent." Employees will go "the additional mile" for you and become devoted promoters of your brand and product if they are actively interested in their job. Temkin Group claims that "engaged personnel are 2.5 times more inclined to stay at work late if something needs to be done after the typical workday finishes" as support for their claim (Wedgewood, 2019).

Boss/Superior

When looking for a work-life balance, people value their managers. Many of the assumptions that make it difficult for workers to strike a work-life balance are created by managers. As said by Heathfield (2021), employees may overlook other prospects for a richer life in their attempts to impress their supervisors and thrive at work. Managers may be an inspiration as well. Managers who prioritize work-life balance in their own lives provide an example for others to follow and encourage staff to do the same. In addition, as stated by Hill (2019), effective managers are aware that their team members need praise and acknowledgment for their efforts and successes. Employees should also be aware that their supervisor's door is always open for them to address any issues they may be having that are preventing them from performing their duties successfully or from being satisfied at work.

Good Relationship with the Co-workers

In line with the study of Hill (2019), employees expect their coworkers to treat them with respect. A hostile workplace, when coworkers are rude or nasty, is typically associated with decreased job satisfaction. Before confrontations worsen and necessitate disciplinary

action, managers must intervene and resolve them. Employees might want a refresher on what actions are unacceptable while communicating with coworkers. Along with McFarlin (2019), she stated that many people who work full-time report that they spend more time with their coworkers than they do with their wives and families. As a result, it's crucial to provide workers the chance to establish meaningful relationships with their coworkers. This may be done by planning unofficial get-togethers away from the office and by promoting staff contact. Small company owners who encourage and enable excellent connections in the workplace can profit in a variety of ways. People are far more likely to work successfully together when they are familiar with one another. Teams with a new member should be observed; normally, the new member will remain fairly secluded as the team learns to know her. The growth of positive connections in the workplace can boost employee morale given how much time people spend with one another. As coworkers complete their responsibilities, they grow friends and enjoy spending time together. These employees could find their jobs to be more enjoyable as a result, leading to an enhanced work environment and morale in general. A rigid and unwelcoming work climate, however, will have the opposite impact. Employees are considerably less likely to desire to look for job at other companies when they feel attached to one, whether it be because they share the same goal as the firm executives or because they feel that their coworkers have become like family. Quality friendships take time to develop, and the thought of having to start from scratch may persuade some employees to remain in their current positions.

Synthesis

Most of the studies mentioned above and the literature viewed opportunities for learning and growth to increase productivity. However, that's all there is to it. Providing employees with opportunities to advance their knowledge and abilities boosts their confidence, which enables them to execute tasks more successfully and efficiently. In addition, Employee development is crucial if employees improve their performance by upgrading their knowledge and abilities.

Job satisfaction is impacted by an employee's views about the fairness of the company wage scale and the current compensation she may be receiving. Therefore, companies need to have a mechanism to evaluate employee performance and provide salary increases to top performers. In addition, opportunities to earn special incentives, such as bonuses, extra paid time off, or vacations, also bring excitement and higher job satisfaction to the workplace. Additionally, a variety of factors, including a healthy work-life balance, positive relationships with superiors and coworkers, and receiving recognition and appreciation from those in the employees' immediate vicinity, might affect their decision to stay with the organization. One of the reasons why employees stay with the firm is because they have a low workload, however studies show that some employees depart for other reasons. The key takeaway from all the material the researchers gathered is that employees' motivations for remaining or leaving the organization rely on their goals, needs, and desires. Depending on their predicament or condition in life, people have a variety of motives for quitting or staying in the organization.

Methodology

Research Design

This study utilized a quantitative approach because it emphasized objective measurements and numerical analysis of data collected through questionnaires and surveys (Babbie, 2010). This study used non-experimental research designs specifically correlational research strategy to arrive with the best results that address the problems. Correlational research strategy is most applicable in this study because it used to establish the relationship of two or more variables. The whole purpose of using correlation in this research is to figure out which variables are connected (Kowalczyk, 2003). Though it tells us that the two variables are related, we cannot say anything about whether one will cause the other. This method does not allow us to come to any conclusions about cause and effect, but an advantage of the correlation method is that we can make predictions about things when we know about correlations. If two variables are correlated, we can predict one based on the other.

Research using a descriptive correlational approach seeks to clarify the connection between several variables without drawing conclusions about causality and effect. It entails gathering and evaluating data on a minimum of two variables to establish a correlation. Descriptive correlational research involves gathering information to elucidate the relevant variables and their relationships. The primary objective is to provide a comprehensive description of the variables and their relationships without influencing them or making any assumptions about their causes and effects (Bhat, 2023). The researchers obtained the frequency and percentage for the age, sex, fields, tenure, and income range of participants in problem 1, as part of the statistical treatment. Problem 2 makes use of standard deviations, average means, and means, while analysis of variance and Pearson r are used for correlation and comparison, respectively.

Respondents

The respondents of this study are forty-four (44) employed or with prior work, 20 years old and above, working or having worked in any of the following settings: a school, an office/corporate, a clinic, or a guidance setting. The researchers used a stratified random sampling since the researcher had a stratum such as employees. The instrument was converted into Google Forms and the published link and was distributed through social media (Messenger) for safety considerations during this time of the COVID-19 pandemic. Due to time constraints, researchers were only able to recruit 44 participants using Google Forms; however, they did verify that all participants were all employees.

Instruments

The researchers were constructed a questionnaire that used to measure the correlation between the demographic profiles and employees' employment reasons for staying and leaving in the companies. This questionnaire is validated by three experts in Psychology and in Research through content validity it refers to how accurately an assessment or measurement tool taps into the various aspect of the specific construct in questions. In other words, do the questions really assess the construct in question, or are the responses by the person answering the questions influenced by other factors (Clause, 2003). In a pilot study that the researchers also did with ten (10) employees, Cronbach's alpha was calculated using Excel, and the result was $\alpha=0.89$, which is interpreted verbally as indicating good internal consistency.

Procedure

The researchers adhere to their plan for collecting data; First, after getting the reliability and validity of the constructed questionnaire, the researchers started to conduct a survey. The researchers exclude the employees who used in the pilot study since they already have an idea about the test; there is no prepared gender if they are qualified in the criteria. Second, all participants agreed to take part and understand the nature of the study by approving the informed consent. The study involved a google form, the researchers assured that the participants are not experienced any harm from the study and any personal information gathered from the study that keep strictly confidential, the participation in the study is voluntary and not required the participants can withdraw from the study, without repercussions, at any time, whether before it starts or during participation. Third, the researchers gave the questionnaires and instructed to answer it seriously to the participants. Lastly, the researchers collected, check and assure that all items in the questionnaire are all answered.

Ethical Considerations

All participants provide informed consent. An informed consent form containing information about procedures, benefits, and risks of participating, an explanation of how to acquire the results of the research, voluntary participation, and contact information about the researchers used. A rationale presented before the first part of the instrumentation; participants oriented about the entire purpose and process of their participation in the research. The researchers assured the participants that all relevant personal data information they disclosed are highly regarded in line with the data privacy act of the Philippines. Further, a statement of confidentiality and adherence to the standards of ethical research served as the foundation of this research undertaking.

Results and Discussion

I. Profile of the Participants

Table 1. Summary of the Profile of the Participants

Table 1.1 Age

<i>Personal Profile</i>	<i>Frequency</i>	<i>Percentage</i>
21-25	7	15.91%
26-30	25	56.82%
31-35	5	11.36%
36-40	4	9.09%
41-45	1	2.27%
46-50	1	2.27%
Above 50	1	2.27%
Total	44	100%

Table 1.2 Sex

<i>Personal Profile</i>	<i>Frequency</i>	<i>Percentage</i>
Male	15	34.09%
Female	29	65.91%
Total	44	100%

Table 1.3 Field

<i>Personal Profile</i>	<i>Frequency</i>	<i>Percentage</i>
Education (Teaching/SPED/School/Institution)	14	31.82%
Industry (Corporate/Company/Organization)	28	63.63%
Clinical (Hospital/Clinic)	2	4.55%
Guidance (School/Institution)	0	0%
Total	44	100%

Table 1.4 *Tenure*

<i>Personal Profile</i>	<i>Frequency</i>	<i>Percentage</i>
Below 6 Months	6	13.63%
6 Months-1 Year	12	27.27%
2-3 Years	10	22.73%
4-5 Years	6	13.64%
More than 5 Years	10	22.73%
Total	44	100%

Table 1.5 *Salary Range*

<i>Personal Profile</i>	<i>Frequency</i>	<i>Percentage</i>
Below PHP 12,000	1	2.27%
PHP 12,000-15,000	7	15.91%
PHP 16,000-20,000	8	18.18%
PHP 21,000-30,000	14	31.82%
PHP 31,000-40,000	7	15.91%
PHP 41,000-50,000	5	11.36%
More than PHP 50,000	2	4.55%
Total	44	100%

Note. The tables present the frequency and percentage distribution of the 44 employed or with prior work individuals in terms of their age, sex, field, tenure, and salary range.

This study included 44 employed or with prior work individuals, with ages range from 21 to 50 years old and above, most of the participants in this research are under the age of 26-30 years old (56.82%). Most of the participants in this research are female with 65.91% and male 34.09%. The Commission on Population and Development (POPCOM) believes that the Philippines might benefit or suffer from a steady increase in the number of working-age citizens, as seen in the most recent official statistics. Among Filipinos, 63.9% are of working age, defined as those between the ages of 15 and 64. This is an increase from 63.3% in 2015 and 59.1% in 2000, according to PSA data. Additionally, the number of women of reproductive age, defined as those between the ages of 15 and 49, reached a new high of 27.8 million in 2020, up from 26 million in 2015 (CEDTyClea, 2022).

In addition, the table displays the participants' field of work; according to the findings, most participants work in industry (63.63%), followed by education (31.82%), clinical (4.55%), and guiding setting (0%). Filipino talents are highly sought after by employers around the globe mainly due to their exceptional work ethic and adaptability. They're known for their resilience and ability to handle pressure, ensuring tasks are completed no matter what. Moreover, their excellent English language skills and cultural adaptability make Filipinos easy to work with, fostering stronger global team collaborations (Kok, 2024).

In addition, Marabe (2022), stated that Employees that are icy, unapproachable, who prefer to be alone in the office do exist. For Filipinos, this is not the situation. Many company owners value the kind and helpful nature of Filipino personnel. Being amiable and welcoming is already ingrained in every Filipino's character. Since most of the participants work in the field, helping coworkers is just second nature to them.

Most participants are in the 6 months to 1-year tenure, which has a percentage of (27.27%), followed by the 2-3 year and more than 5-year tenures, which have a percentage of (22.73%), and the less than 6 month and 4-5-year tenures have a percentage of (13.63%). According to Bantilan (2024), When compared to other nations, the Philippines' employment laws are unique. When it comes to labor protections and guaranteed tenure security, the Philippines takes a pro-labor stance. Most of the participants in this research fall into the 6-month to 1-year bracket because of the several types of job classifications in the Philippines, including probationary, regular, permanent, and fixed-term/contractual.

The table also shows the participants' salaries, with most of them being between P21,000 and P30,000 (31.82%), P16,000 and P20,000 (18.18%), P12,000 and P15,000, P31,000 and P40,000 (15.91%), P41,000 and P50,000 (11.36%), More than P50,000 (4.55%), and the lowest being below P12,000 (2.27%). This sector is so important to the economy that it was even acknowledged by the World Trade Organization in 2019. But there are those who persist in the false belief that "cheap labor" is the driving force for outsourcing to developing nations. Reason being, the Philippines is still a developing nation, so its living costs and expenditures are relatively modest. An average monthly wage of Php 18,423.00 was reported in the 2022 Occupational Wage Survey (OWS) for the Philippines. Workers' pays in the Philippines could vary by region, sector, and level of expertise due to the absence of a uniform minimum wage (Estrellado, 2024). The minimum wage in the Philippines is PHP 610.00 for non-agricultural establishments and PHP 573.00 for agricultural, service/retail, and manufacturing establishments that routinely employ 10 or fewer people. For non-agricultural industries in Metro Manila, the minimum wage ranges from around PHP 500 to PHP 700 per day, however it does vary by business categorization (Uppala, 2024).

II. Respondents Rate their Employment Reasons for Staying and Leaving

The constructed questionnaire was used to assess the participants' reasons for staying and leaving the companies (Group and Development, Compensation and Benefits, Work Life Balance, Boss/Superior and Good Relationship with the co-workers).

Table 2.1 *Growth and Development*

Indicators	Mean	SD	Qualitative Description	Verbal Interpretation	Ranking
Staying					
1. I continue to work for the company, in part, because I get to accomplish interesting and challenging things at work.	3.34	0.71	Strongly Agree	Very High	1
2. One of the reasons I continue to work for the company is that they provide enough opportunities for training to keep my knowledge and skills up to date.	3.18	0.79	Agree	High	2
3. When I know that my employer promotes individuals who work hard and deserves long-tenured employees, I continue to work there.	3.34	0.89	Strongly Agree	Very High	1
Average	3.29	0.65	Strongly Agree	Very High	
Leaving					
1. When the work is monotonous and without excitement, and the company does not offer seminars or training to its employees, I prefer to quit because there is no longer any opportunity for personal or professional growth.	2.02	0.98	Disagree	Low	3
2. After a year of employment, if the employer does not offer me a promotion or even a pay raise, I will be departing.	2.30	1.05	Disagree	Low	1
3. Even though I think the organization supports personal and professional growth, I think there are other aspects that make me want to leave the company.	2.07	0.85	Disagree	Low	2
Average	2.13	0.65	Disagree	Low	

Legend: 3.25-4.00 Very High, 2.50-3.24 High, 1.75-2.49 Low, 1.00-1.74 Very Low

In statements 1 and 3 of the reason for staying with the highest mean of 3.34 the respondents strongly agree that they continue to work for the company, in part, because they get to accomplish interesting and challenging things at work and when they know that the employer promotes individuals who work hard and deserves long-tenured employees, they continue to work there. Also, in statement 2 with the lowest mean of 3.18, the respondents agree that one of the reasons they continue to work for the company is that they provide enough opportunities for training to keep their knowledge and skills up to date.

In statement 2 of the reason for leaving with the highest mean of 2.30 the respondents disagree that after a year of employment if the employer does not offer them a promotion or even a pay raise, they will be departing. In addition, in statement 1 with the lowest mean of 2.02, the respondents disagree that when the work is monotonous and without excitement, and the company does not offer seminars or training to its employees, they prefer to quit because there is no longer any opportunity for personal or professional growth.

Table 2.2 *Compensation and Benefits*

Indicators	Mean	SD	Qualitative Description	Verbal Interpretation	Ranking
Staying					
1. When the employer shows appreciation for my work or length of service by raising my pay/ allowances/ additional benefits (life insurance, an HMO, a transportation allowance, a rice subsidy, an internet allowance, bonuses or etc.) for employees. I continue to work there.	3.68	0.60	Strongly Agree	Very High	1
2. If the company pays a wage, it will be sufficient for me and my family to meet our material demands and needs. I stay the company.	3.41	0.69	Strongly Agree	Very High	2
3. One of the reasons I stay with the company is because they pay my salary and my mandatory benefits (SSS, PhilHealth, and PAGIBIG) on time.	3.18	0.90	Agree	High	3
Average	3.42	0.51	Strongly Agree	Very High	
Leaving					
1. Even though I have enough or high salary, my employer has rewarded me for my achievements by increasing my compensation, adding new benefits, or offering me other incentives. I still left the company, though, for other reasons.	2.41	1.06	Disagree	Low	1
2. My salary is a major consideration; if it is insufficient to cover my demands and needs, I quit the job.	1.95	0.81	Disagree	Low	3
3. One of the reasons I left the company was due to the late payment of my mandatory benefits (SSS, PhilHealth, and PAGIBIG) and salary, both of which caused me a lot of problems.	2.39	1.13	Disagree	Low	2
Average	2.25	0.59	Disagree	Low	

Legend: 3.25-4.00 Very High, 2.50-3.24 High, 1.75-2.49 Low, 1.00-1.74 Very Low

In statement 1 of the reason for staying with the highest mean of 3.68 the respondents strongly agree that when the employer shows appreciation for their work or length of service by raising their pay/ allowances/ additional benefits (life insurance, an HMO, a transportation allowance, a rice subsidy, an internet allowance, bonuses or etc.) for employees. They continue to work there. In

statement 3 with the lowest mean of 3.18, the respondents agree that one of the reasons they stay with the company is because the company pay their salary and mandatory benefits (SSS, PhilHealth, and PAGIBIG) on time.

In statement 1 of the reason for leaving of employees with the highest mean of 2.41 the respondents disagree that even though they have enough or high salary, their employer has rewarded them for their achievements by increasing the compensation, adding new benefits, or offering them other incentives. They still left the company, though, for other reasons. In addition, in statement 2 with the lowest mean of 2.39, the respondents disagree that one of the reasons they left the company was due to the late payment of their mandatory benefits (SSS, PhilHealth, and PAGIBIG) and salary, both of which caused them a lot of problems.

Table 2.3 Work Life Balance

Indicators	Mean	SD	Qualitative Description	Verbal Interpretation	Ranking
Staying					
1. If my employer gives me the time to travel alone or with my family while maintaining my balance between work, social obligations, and personal leisure. I continue to work there.	3.52	0.73	Strongly Agree	Very High	1
2. If the company did not force the employees to work beyond working hours. I continue to work for the company in part because of it.	3.34	0.71	Strongly Agree	Very High	3
3. I continue to work for a company that helps its employees whenever they have emergencies or other personal problems.	3.43	0.79	Strongly Agree	Very High	2
Average	3.43	0.60	Strongly Agree	Very High	
Leaving					
1. Even though I have a good work-life balance, other reasons prevent me from staying at the company despite this.	2.14	0.82	Disagree	Low	2
2. One of the reasons I left the company was because they required overtime or after-hours labor from their staff.	2.39	0.99	Disagree	Low	1
3. The employer requires me to work even when I have an emergency or personal concern at home, which is the reason I left the job because I did not have time for my family in case of emergency.	2.11	1.10	Disagree	Low	3
Average	2.21	0.66	Disagree	Low	

Legend: 3.25-4.00 Very High, 2.50-3.24 High, 1.75-2.49 Low, 1.00-1.74 Very Low

In statement 1 of the reason for staying with the highest mean of 3.52 the respondents strongly agree that if the employer gives them the time to travel alone or with their family while maintaining the balance between work, social obligations, and personal leisure, they continue to work there. In statement 2 with the lowest mean of 3.34, the respondents strongly agree that if the company did not force the employees to work beyond working hours, they continue to work for the company in part because of it.

In statement 2 of the reason for leaving of employees with the highest mean of 2.39 the respondents disagree that one of the reasons they left the company was because they required overtime or after-hours labor from their staff. In addition, in statement 3 with the lowest mean of 2.11, the employer requires them to work even when they have an emergency or personal concern at home, which is the reason they left the job because they did not have time for their family in case of emergency.

Table 2.4 Boss/Superior

Indicators	Mean	SD	Qualitative Description	Verbal Interpretation	Ranking
Staying					
1. If my boss/manager supports me in my work, encourages me, and shows appreciation for what I do. I am motivated to remain with the company.	3.66	0.61	Strongly Agree	Very High	1
2. I continue to work for the organization because my superior provides honest and helpful feedback to help me improve my work and always looks for my areas of strength.	3.52	0.76	Strongly Agree	Very High	2
3. My boss and I have a positive working relationship, which keeps me stay in the company.	3.32	0.86	Strongly Agree	Very High	3
Average	3.50	0.61	Strongly Agree	Very High	
Leaving					
1. Even if I get along well with my boss professionally, there are still other issues preventing me from staying.	2.11	0.87	Disagree	Low	2
2. One of the reasons I left the company was that, for the most part, my boss did not recognize the effort I put into my work and was constantly on the lookout for my mistakes.	2.14	1.03	Disagree	Low	1
3. I leave the organization due to the toxic and distressing atmosphere created by the boss.	1.91	1.14	Strongly Disagree	Very Low	3
Average	2.05	0.77	Disagree	Low	

Legend: 3.25-4.00 Very High, 2.50-3.24 High, 1.75-2.49 Low, 1.00-1.74 Very Low

In statement 1 of the reason for staying with the highest mean of 3.66 the respondents strongly agree that if the boss/manager supports them in their work, encourages them, and shows appreciation for what they do, they motivated to remain with the company. In statement 3 with the lowest mean of 3.32, the respondents strongly agree that if the boss and the employee have a positive working relationship, which keeps them stay in the company.

In statement 2 of the reason for leaving of employees with the highest mean of 2.14 the respondents disagree that one of the reasons they left the company was that, for the most part, their boss did not recognize the effort they put into their work and was constantly on the lookout for their mistakes. In addition, in statement 3 with the lowest mean of 1.91, they leave the organization due to the toxic and distressing atmosphere created by the boss.

Table 2.5 Good Relationship with the Co-workers

Indicators	Mean	SD	Qualitative Description	Verbal Interpretation	Ranking
Staying					
1. One of the reasons I continue to work for the company is because of the positive working relationships I have with my coworkers, and considering one another as family.	3.61	0.65	Strongly Agree	Very High	1
2. I continue to work for the company because I trust my coworkers and feel comfortable sharing difficult times in my personal or professional life with them.	3.55	0.70	Strongly Agree	Very High	2
3. My coworkers make me look forward to going to work because they constantly lend a hand and encourage me to complete tasks more quickly. Even though my job is challenging, I don't mind as long as I'm with my coworkers, and that's what keeps me stay in the company.	3.55	0.70	Strongly Agree	Very High	2
Average	3.57	0.57	Strongly Agree	Very High	
Leaving					
1. Even if my coworkers and I get along well and treat one another like family, there are still other issues that prevent me from staying at the company.	2.00	0.94	Disagree	Low	1
2. If my coworkers do not assist and support me, especially when I am struggling to complete the job, and they seem happy that I am having a difficult time. I leave the company.	2.00	1.03	Disagree	Low	1
3. If I no longer look forward to going to work because I feel that I work in a toxic environment because of my coworkers who constantly criticize me, I leave the organization.	1.64	0.84	Strongly Disagree	Very Low	2
Average	1.88	0.68	Disagree	Low	

Legend: 3.25-4.00 Very High, 2.50-3.24 High, 1.75-2.49 Low, 1.00-1.74 Very Low

In statement 1 of the reason for staying with the highest mean of 3.61 the respondents strongly agree that one of the reasons they continue to work for the company is because of the positive working relationships they have with their coworkers, and considering one another as family. In statements 2 and 3 with the lowest mean of 3.55, the respondents strongly agree that they continue to work for the company because they trust their coworkers and feel comfortable sharing difficult times in their personal or professional life with them and their coworkers make them look forward to going to work because they constantly lend a hand and encourage them to complete tasks more quickly. Even though their job is challenging, they don't mind as long as they are with their coworkers, and that's what keeps them stay in the company.

In statements 1 and 2 of the reason for leaving of employees with the highest mean of 2.00 the respondents disagree that even if their coworkers and them get along well and treat one another like family, there are still other issues that prevent them from staying at the company and if their coworkers do not assist and support them, especially when they are struggling to complete the job, and they seem happy that they are having a difficult time. they leave the company. In addition, in statement 3 with the lowest mean of 1.64, If they are no longer look forward to going to work because they feel that they work in a toxic environment because of their coworkers who constantly criticize them, they leave the organization.

III. Relationship between Demographic Profiles and Employees' Employment Reasons for Staying and Leaving

Table 3.1 shows the relationship between Age and Employees' Employment Reasons for Staying and Leaving. The analysis revealed that age has no significant relationship to the growth and development with the Pearson r of (ROS=0.16) with a p-value of 0.296 and (ROL=0.27) with a p-value of 0.076, compensation and benefits with the Pearson r of (ROS=0.11) with a p-value of 0.485 and (ROL=0.12) with a p-value of 0.451, work life balance with the Pearson r of (ROS=-0.07) with a p-value of 0.674, boss/superior with the Pearson r of (ROS=0.11) with a p-value of 0.483 and (ROL=0.29) with a p-value of 0.06, and good relationship with the co-workers with the Pearson r of (ROS=0.05) with a p-value of 0.744. The weak significant relationship of age is work life balance with the Pearson r of (ROL=0.33) with a p-value of 0.027 and good relationship with the co-workers with the Pearson r of (ROL=0.32) with a p-value of 0.033. The computed values are found to be a significant, do not accept the null hypothesis. Therefore, we can infer that age has a significant relationship with work life balance (Reason for Leaving) and good relationship with the co-workers (Reason for

Leaving).

Table 3.1 Relationship between Age and Employees' Employment Reasons for Staying and Leaving

		AGE			
		Pearson r	p-value	Degree of Correlation	Remarks
Growth and Development	Reason for Staying	0.16	0.296	Very Weak	Not Significant
	Reason for Leaving	0.27	0.076	Weak	Not Significant
Compensation and Benefits	Reason for Staying	0.11	0.485	Very Weak	Not Significant
	Reason for Leaving	0.12	0.451	Very Weak	Not Significant
Work Life Balance	Reason for Staying	-0.07	0.674	Very Weak	Not Significant
	Reason for Leaving	0.33	0.027	Weak	Significant
Boss/Superior	Reason for Staying	0.11	0.483	Very Weak	Not Significant
	Reason for Leaving	0.29	0.06	Weak	Not Significant
Good Relationship with the Co-Workers	Reason for Staying	0.05	0.744	Very Weak	Not Significant
	Reason for Leaving	0.32	0.033	Weak	Significant

*Significant at .05

*ROS=Reason for staying, ROL=Reason for leaving

Table 3.2 Relationship between Sex and Employees' Employment Reasons for Staying and Leaving

		SEX			
		Pearson r	p-value	Degree of Correlation	Remarks
Growth and Development	Reason for Staying	0.10	0.522	Very Weak	Not Significant
	Reason for Leaving	0.09	0.545	Very Weak	Not Significant
Compensation and Benefits	Reason for Staying	-0.03	0.858	Very Weak	Not Significant
	Reason for Leaving	0.06	0.693	Very Weak	Not Significant
Work Life Balance	Reason for Staying	0.17	0.260	Very Weak	Not Significant
	Reason for Leaving	0.01	0.936	Very Weak	Not Significant
Boss/Superior	Reason for Staying	0.14	0.350	Very Weak	Not Significant
	Reason for Leaving	-0.12	0.444	Very Weak	Not Significant
Good Relationship with the Co-Workers	Reason for Staying	0.10	0.513	Very Weak	Not Significant
	Reason for Leaving	0.11	0.486	Very Weak	Not Significant

*Significant at .05

*ROS=Reason for staying, ROL=Reason for leaving

Table 3.2 shows the relationship between Sex and Employees' Employment Reasons for Staying and Leaving. The analysis revealed that sex has no significant relationship to all variables such as growth and development with the Pearson r of (ROS=0.10) with a p-value of 0.522 and (ROL=0.09) with a p-value of 0.545, compensation and benefits with the Pearson r of (ROS=-0.03) with a p-value of 0.858 and (ROL=0.06) with a p-value of 0.693, work life balance with the Pearson r of (ROS=0.17) with a p-value of 0.260 and (ROL=0.01) with a p-value of 0.936, boss/superior with the Pearson r of (ROS=0.14) with a p-value of 0.350 and (ROL=-0.12) with a p-value of 0.444, and good relationship with the co-workers with the Pearson r of (ROS=0.10) with a p-value of 0.513 and (ROL=0.11) with a p-value of 0.486. The computed values are found to be not significant, do not accept the alternative hypothesis. Therefore, we can infer that sex has no significant relationship to all values of reasons of employees' employment for staying and leaving.

Table 3.3 Relationship between Field and Employees' Employment Reasons for Staying and Leaving

		FIELD			
		Pearson r	p-value	Degree of Correlation	Remarks
Growth and Development	Reason for Staying	-0.01	0.929	Very Weak	Not Significant
	Reason for Leaving	0.04	0.816	Very Weak	Not Significant
Compensation and Benefits	Reason for Staying	-0.10	0.504	Very Weak	Not Significant
	Reason for Leaving	0.26	0.084	Weak	Not Significant
Work Life Balance	Reason for Staying	-0.11	0.495	Very Weak	Not Significant
	Reason for Leaving	0.31	0.038	Weak	Significant
Boss/Superior	Reason for Staying	0.09	0.548	Very Weak	Not Significant
	Reason for Leaving	0.11	0.481	Very Weak	Not Significant
Good Relationship with the Co-Workers	Reason for Staying	0.04	0.812	Very Weak	Not Significant
	Reason for Leaving	0.26	0.084	Weak	Not Significant

*Significant at .05

*ROS=Reason for staying, ROL=Reason for leaving

Table 3.3 shows the relationship between Field and Employees' Employment Reasons for Staying and Leaving. The analysis revealed that field of work has no significant relationship to growth and development with the Pearson r of (ROS=-0.01) with a p-value of 0.929 and (ROL=0.04) with a p-value of 0.816, compensation and benefits with the Pearson r of (ROS=-0.10) with a p-value of 0.504 and (ROL=0.26) with a p-value of 0.084, work life balance with the Pearson r of (ROS=-0.11) with a p-value of 0.495, boss/superior with the Pearson r of (ROS=0.09) with a p-value of 0.548 and (ROL=0.11) with a p-value of 0.481, and good relationship with the co-workers with the Pearson r of (ROS=0.04) with a p-value of 0.812 and (ROL=0.26) with a p-value of 0.084. The weak significant relationship of field is work life balance with the Pearson r of (ROL=0.31) with a p-value of 0.038. The computed value is found to be

a significant, do not accept the null hypothesis. Therefore, we can infer that field of work has a significant relationship with work life balance (Reason for Leaving).

Table 3.4 Relationship between Tenure and Employees' Employment Reasons for Staying and Leaving

		TENURE			
		Pearson r	p-value	Degree of Correlation	Remarks
Growth and Development	Reason for Staying	-0.12	0.442	Very Weak	Not Significant
	Reason for Leaving	0.29	0.06	Weak	Not Significant
Compensation and Benefits	Reason for Staying	0.08	0.603	Very Weak	Not Significant
	Reason for Leaving	0.29	0.06	Weak	Not Significant
Work Life Balance	Reason for Staying	-0.04	0.784	Very Weak	Not Significant
	Reason for Leaving	0.27	0.077	Weak	Not Significant
Boss/Superior	Reason for Staying	-0.13	0.406	Very Weak	Not Significant
	Reason for Leaving	0.17	0.264	Very Weak	Not Significant
Good Relationship with the Co-Workers	Reason for Staying	-0.22	0.149	Weak	Not Significant
	Reason for Leaving	0.34	0.022	Weak	Significant

*Significant at .05

*ROS=Reason for staying, ROL=Reason for leaving

Table 3.4 shows the relationship between Tenure and Employees' Employment Reasons for Staying and Leaving. The analysis revealed that tenure has no significant relationship to growth and development with the Pearson r of (ROS=-0.12) with a p-value of 0.442 and (ROL=0.29) with a p-value of 0.06, compensation and benefits with the Pearson r of (ROS=0.08) with a p-value of 0.603 and (ROL=0.29) with a p-value of 0.06, work life balance with the Pearson r of (ROS=-0.04) with a p-value of 0.784 and (ROL=0.27) with a p-value of 0.077, boss/superior with the Pearson r of (ROS=-0.13) with a p-value of 0.406 and (ROL=0.17) with a p-value of 0.264, and good relationship with the co-workers with the Pearson r of (ROS=-0.22) with a p-value of 0.149. The weak significant relationship of tenure is good relationship with the co-workers with the Pearson r of (ROL=0.34) with a p-value of 0.022. The computed value is found to be a significant, do not accept the null hypothesis. Therefore, we can infer that tenure has a significant relationship with good relationship with the co-workers (Reason for Leaving).

Table 3.5 Relationship between Salary Range and Employees' Employment Reasons for Staying and Leaving

		SALARY RANGE			
		Pearson r	p-value	Degree of Correlation	Remarks
Growth and Development	Reason for Staying	0.33	0.030	Weak	Significant
	Reason for Leaving	0.34	0.026	Weak	Significant
Compensation and Benefits	Reason for Staying	-0.16	0.294	Very Weak	Not Significant
	Reason for Leaving	0.07	0.661	Very Weak	Not Significant
Work Life Balance	Reason for Staying	-0.01	0.933	Very Weak	Not Significant
	Reason for Leaving	0.23	0.136	Weak	Not Significant
Boss/Superior	Reason for Staying	0.03	0.866	Very Weak	Not Significant
	Reason for Leaving	0.19	0.215	Very Weak	Not Significant
Good Relationship with the Co-Workers	Reason for Staying	-0.03	0.831	Very Weak	Not Significant
	Reason for Leaving	0.18	0.234	Very Weak	Not Significant

*Significant at .05

*ROS=Reason for staying, ROL=Reason for leaving

Table 3.5 shows the relationship between Salary Range and Employees' Employment Reasons for Staying and Leaving. The analysis revealed that salary range has no significant relationship to compensation and benefits with the Pearson r of (ROS=-0.16) with a p-value of 0.294 and (ROL=0.07) with a p-value of 0.661, work life balance with the Pearson r of (ROS=-0.01) with a p-value of 0.933 and (ROL=0.23) with a p-value of 0.136, boss/superior with the Pearson r of (ROS=0.03) with a p-value of 0.866 and (ROL=0.19) with a p-value of 0.215, and good relationship with the co-workers with the Pearson r of (ROS=-0.03) with a p-value of 0.831 and (ROL=0.18) with a p-value of 0.234. The weak significant relationship of salary range are growth and development with the Pearson r of (ROS=0.33) with a p-value of 0.030 and (ROL=0.34) with a p-value of 0.026. The computed values are found to be a significant, do not accept the null hypothesis. Therefore, we can infer that salary range has a significant relationship with growth and development both for Reason for staying and leaving).

Table 4.0 Differences between employees' employment reasons for staying and leaving

	p-value	Remarks
Growth and Development (Staying and Leaving)	0.045	Significant
Compensation and Benefits (Staying and Leaving)	0.429	Not significant
Work Life Balance (Staying and Leaving)	0.008	Significant
Boss/Superior (Staying and Leaving)	0.000	Significant
Good Relationship with the Co-Workers (Staying and Leaving)	0.690	Not significant

*Significant at .05

Table 4.0 shows the differences between employees' employment reasons for staying and leaving. The analysis revealed that compensation and benefits reason for staying and leaving has no significant differences with a p-value of 0.429, good relationship with

the co-worker's reason for staying and leaving also has no significant differences with a p-value of 0.690. Furthermore, growth and development with a p-value of 0.045, work life balance with a p-value of 0.008, and boss/superior reasons for staying and leaving with a p-value of 0.000 has a significant difference, do not accept the null hypothesis. Therefore, we can infer that the employees' reason for staying and leaving the company are both or either the following: growth and development, work life balance and boss/superior.

Conclusion

Most study participants, according to the researchers, are between the ages of 26 and 30 because this is the age range in which people put the greatest effort into making their lives successful. It is supported by study of (OECD,2021) employment rates for four age groups are people aged 15-64 (the working age population): people aged 15 to 24 (those just entering the labor market following education); people aged 25 to 54 (those in their prime working lives); people aged 55 to 64 (those passing the peak of their career and approaching retirement). In addition, the bulk of the participants in this study are women because women grew up with movements like TimesUp, MeToo, and BlackLivesMatter, which offered them greater tools and perspectives on fair, respectful treatment, according to the study by BasuMallick, 2021. The majority of participants work in industry, as opposed to those who work in educational settings, counseling, or hospitals, which require additional credentials in order for people to work in such sectors. Most participants have a tenure of between six months and a year since the majority of participants is under the range of 26-30 years old, they are considered in generation Y, Gen Y, or Millennials, were born between 1981 and 1994/6. They are currently between 25 and 40 years old. Additionally, they are in the process of investing in their lives. When it comes to participant salary, the most majority are in the P21,000–P30,000, In the Philippines, it serves as the standard base for pay for those who have more than a month or less than a year of working in the company.

The research concludes people stay employed by a company that keeps their jobs fascinating. Even when a job is challenging, it is made exciting and thrilling so that employees don't feel bored with their tasks. Additionally, long-tenured employees stay with the company if the employer promotes them, increases their pay, allowances, or other benefits to show appreciation for their performance or length of service, also, employers allow them to spend time with their families or alone to have a healthy balance between work, social obligations, and personal time off, and supports and encourages them in their career. Treat one another like family is one of the reasons why employees stick with the company. Moreover, people still stay in the company even they are not given a promotion or even a wage boost, Employee retention is mostly dependent on how well compensated they are, if at all. People continue to work for the company even though it insisted on making them put in extra or after-hours labor, and even though their boss was constantly on the watch for their mistakes and did not value the effort they put into their work. According to the findings, even when their coworkers are poisonous or don't treat them like family, they continue to work for the organization.

The importance of a work-life balance and positive relationships with coworkers increases with age, therefore whether an employee is older or younger, it might be a factor in their decision to quit an organization. Why workers remain at the firm or leave has nothing to do with their gender. Employees may quit the organization for several reasons, including poisonous or challenging working conditions. Employees place a high value on work-life balance; if they don't feel like they have enough time for themselves or their families, it might be another reason why they leave the organization. Additionally, the better the relationship with coworkers, the longer the tenure; yet, the researchers also draw the conclusion that if one close coworker departed, the other close coworker may follow suit. Last but not least, salaries also have a role in employees staying or leaving a firm.

Work-life balance, boss or superior motives for staying or leaving, and personal growth and development are unrelated. The researchers come to the conclusion that work-life balance, growth and development, and boss/superior are all or some of the reasons why employees stay with or leave a company.

Based on the findings of the study, several recommendations have been formulated: The organizations may develop a programs, training, or seminars about mental health prevention, the researcher recommends that the HR Department or Industrial Organizational Development practitioners may raise the focus on mental health prevention, promotion, and education.

The researcher suggests posting flyers, hosting meetings with various staff groups to discuss the retention strategy and posting the policy on the business website. The task of putting the plan into action can fall under the purview of a department or committee. It is crucial to make sure that those in charge of the implementation process have received the necessary training to comprehend the problems that arise in the workplace.

The study also suggests counseling sessions or interview or “kamustahan” to assist staff in leading good mental lifestyles. This recommendation may be helpful to managers, supervisors, and human resources staff.

The study's conclusions should aid future researchers who are interested in conducting the same study to make improvements or even to refute the study's findings to identify additional factors influencing the variables provided. Additionally, advised is conducting the research in several locations.

References

Babbie, E. R. (2010). *The practice of social research* (12th ed.). Belmont, CA: Wadsworth Cengage.

Bantilan, D.J. (2024). 6 Common employee classifications in Philippines as to security of tenure - Tax and Accounting Center, Inc.

(n.d.). <https://taxactcenter.ph/common-employee-classifications-security-of-tenure-philippines/>

Bhat, A. (2023, November 24). Descriptive Correlational: Descriptive vs Correlational Research. QuestionPro. <https://www.questionpro.com/blog/descriptive-research-vs-correlational-research/>

Boogaard, K. (2020). Five Totally Valid Reasons to Stay in a Job You Hate. <https://www.themuse.com/advice/5-totally-valid-reasons-to-stay-in-a-job-you-hate>

Chamberlain, A., (2017). What Matters More to Your Workforce than Money. <https://hbr.org/2017/01/what-matters-more-to-your-workforce-than-money>

CEDTyClea. (2022, August 15). Steady growth in PHL working age population could be a boon or bane, says POPCOM. BusinessWorld Online. <https://www.bworldonline.com/the-nation/2022/08/15/468505/steady-growth-in-phl-working-age-population-could-be-a-boon-or-bane-says-popcom/>

Crisostomo, K., (2023). 29% of Filipino workers want to leave current employers. (n.d.). Philippine News Agency. <https://www.pna.gov.ph/articles/1207100>

Estrellado, V. (2024, February 20). Average salary in the Philippines: How a company saves costs through Filipino hires. Outsource Accelerator. <https://www.outsourceaccelerator.com/articles/average-salary-in-the-philippines/>

Hastwell, C., (2021). Creating a Culture of Recognition (<https://www.greatplacetowork.com/resources/blog/creating-a-culture-of-recognition>).

Heathfield, S., (2021). A Checklist for the Retention of Your Talented Employees. <https://www.thebalancecareers.com/top-reasons-why-employees-quit-their-job-1918985>

Heathfield, S., (2021). Prioritize Other Aspects of Life Such as Family Relationships. <https://www.thebalancecareers.com/work-life-balance-1918292>

Hill, B., (2019). What Are the Factors Affecting Job Satisfaction. <https://smallbusiness.chron.com/factors-affecting-job-satisfaction-20114.html>

Kok, E. (2024, January 29). Why foreign companies love to hire Filipinos? Remotify PH. <https://remotify.ph/blogs/international-employers-choose-filipino-workers/>

Marabe, L. (2022, January 16). The Filipino employees: their work culture and characteristics – Offshore accountancy outsourcing. Intelligent Outsourcing. <https://intelligentoutsourcing.co.uk/the-filipino-employees-their-work-culture-and-characteristics/>

McFarlin, K., (2019). Importance of Relationships in the Workplace. <https://smallbusiness.chron.com/importance-relationships-workplace-10380.html>

Sanfilippo, M., (2022). How to Improve Your Work-Life Balance Today. <https://www.businessnewsdaily.com/5244-improve-work-life-balance-today.html>

Uppala, S. K. (2024, March 26). Average salary in Philippines. Time Champ - Time and Productivity Tracker. <https://www.timechamp.io/blogs/average-salary-in-philippines/>

Wedgewood, J., (2019). The Importance of Work-Life Balance (<https://thehappinessindex.com/blog/importance-work-life-balance>).

Wooll, M., (2022). Compensation and benefits: Why the right pay and perks still matter. <https://www.betterup.com/blog/compensation-and-benefits>

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